

How did XF-ACTORS contribute to the work of NPPOs

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The European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) is a regional standard-setting organization in plant health. One of EPPO's main priorities is to prevent the introduction of dangerous pests from other parts of the world, and to limit their spread within the region should they be introduced. After the introduction of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the region, the first priority for the organization has been the revision of the Diagnostic protocol (first adopted in 2004). Standards on inspection of consignments and place of production have also been prepared. EPPO has also initiated the revision of the certification scheme for olive plants for planting, benefiting from the contacts and technical discussions made during participation in the development of the XF-ACTORS Voluntary System Preventing Pests (VSPP). EPPO also initiated the revision of the certification scheme for olive plants for planting, benefiting from the contacts and technical discussions made during participation in the development of the XF-ACTORS Voluntary System Preventing Pests (VSPP). Finally, discussions between modelers and risk managers have been organized in the framework of the project. The contribution of XF-ACTORS to the revision of these Standards will be highlighted as well as other activities conducted with XF-ACTORS partners which are of benefit to National Plant Protection Organizations.